

Headspace: Encouraging Stress Reduction and Mindfulness in First Responders Through Using a Mobile Application

Anika Simpson, DNP, PMHNP-BC, FNP-C,
Raymund Gantioque, DNP, ACNP-BC -- Taqialdeen Zamil, DNP, RN, PMHNP-BC

Background

- 30% of first responders experience conditions like depression and PTSD
- The World Trade Center attacks led 11% of respondents to develop PTSD with half experience anxiety and depression
- Suicide rates remain high with 125 - 300 police personnel ending their life each year
- Suicide accounted for twice as many officer fatalities in 2019 as deaths in the line of duty
- 646 of 3,645 police fatalities over a 22-year study were ascribed to occupational ailments

Purpose

To address the contributing factors to increased stress levels and decreased mindfulness in first responders

- Police Officers
- Dispatchers
- Forensic Specialists

Problem

Does Implementing the Headspace Mobile Application decrease perceived stress and increase mindfulness in first responders?

This photo by Unknown Author is licensed under CC BY-NC-ND

Methods

- **Setting:** A local law-enforcement agency in LA County
- **Design:** Pre-and post-test
- **Sample:** 13 First Responders
- **Instrument:** PSS-10 and MAAS-15 survey scales
- **Intervention:** Headspace Mobile App
- **Data Analysis:** Paired t-test

Johns Hopkins Nursing Evidence Based Model

Results

The result of the two-tailed paired samples *t*-test was significant based on an alpha value of .05, $t(9) = 6.00, p < .001$

The result of the two-tailed paired samples *t*-test was significant based on an alpha value of .05, $t(14) = -6.50, p < .001$

Limitations

- Small sample size which limits generalizability of results
- Reliance on self-report measures
- Participants busy schedules

Recommendations

- Promoting Mindfulness Interventions
- Provide information on the benefits of mindfulness practices, evidence-based strategies for incorporating mindfulness into daily life
- Integrate Mobile Mindfulness interventions like Headspace into stress management programs

Conclusions

- This quality improvement project provides evidence for the effectiveness of the Headspace Mindfulness Mobile app in reducing perceived stress and enhancing mindfulness levels among first responders.
- The significant improvements observed on both the PSS-10 and MAAS-15 scales underestimate the potential of mobile mindfulness interventions in promoting psychological well-being.

References

